

The surprising challenge in having a bicycle stolen: a small scale investigation into bicycle theft on the streets of Melbourne, Australia

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Abstract

Three low end bicycles were fitted with covert GPS tracking devices, secured in public places and left to be stolen. Two of the three bicycles were stolen during the experiments time frame allowing us to capture a small amount of data on how stolen bicycles are used and distributed.

While the small sample size ($n=3$) makes concrete conclusions difficult, this paper hopes to aid further research in this field by providing insight into decision making and planning for similar experiments.

It also identified tentatively that common prior assumptions regarding the quick resale of stolen goods may be false.

1. Introduction

After several department researchers had first hand experience with theft of their bicycles, an experiment was developed. We aimed to investigate the motives behind bicycle theft, the likelihood of the theft and hopefully shed some light on the overall supply chain of the bicycle black market.

This paper introduces a novel approach to creating "bait bikes" which can be used to validate theories in this area.

A cursory search did not uncover significant research performed on the theft of low end bicycles, however the research team have no shortage of anecdotal data on the theft of low end bicycles.

We wished firstly to determine the actual risk of leaving a bicycle secured overnight in public spaces around Melbourne, Victoria as we found that not knowing this caused difficulty in personal risk based decisions.

In "Tracking stolen bikes in Amsterdam" [1] it was shown that many stolen bicycles were being sold on. However it appears that little attention was paid to our subject of particular interest - bicycles that one would think would not be valuable enough to take the risk of stealing.

The assumption was that stolen bicycles would be promptly resold on largely unregulated person-to-person marketplaces such as Facebook or Gumtree, however our results imply that this might not always be the case or this may occur after a much longer time than expected. We also aimed to identify if the bicycles pass through different groups/people, are sold interstate, or

are sold directly.

The tracking performed in this research was not intended to identify any specific individual who may have committed the theft. No information on the theft of these bicycles has been reported to the authorities. We also aimed to avoid tracking the bicycle should it be resold to an unknowing third party, so we are continuing ongoing efforts to locate and purchase it in the event that it appears for sale on the open market.

2. Methodology

Three bicycles were purchased from a major retailer at a significant discount due to minor pre-existing damage. These bicycles were of varying quality and style. We ruled out sourcing from the second hand market as we did not want to risk conducting the experiment with an already stolen bicycle.

The bicycles were fitted with GPS trackers that report their position using the 4G mobile phone network. We chose this approach over other options like the Apple AirTag or Tile tracker, because active network based trackers offer more accurate positioning, more frequent updates, and will not trigger anti-tracking warnings on mobile phones that stay in close proximity to them.

Serial numbers of the bicycles were kept on file in case the bicycles were collected by council authorities or impounded by law enforcement.

The bicycles were transported by train, then either walked or ridden from the station to arbitrarily selected areas which we personally felt were hotspots for theft.

Photographs of the bicycles at their last known location were then taken discreetly.

Bicycle movement was tracked via GPS, and if a bicycle was seen to leave the area, it was deemed to be stolen. Facebook Marketplace and Gumtree were then monitored daily for a bicycle with the same distinct features. Our intent was to ensure we purchased the bicycle before anyone else from the general public did. Tracking would cease if we believed that the bicycle had been sold to an unrelated third party.

2.1. Tracker

The bicycles were fitted with Tracki GPS trackers which provide location reporting via a combination of WiFi, Bluetooth and GPS positioning over a MTM LTE connection. The tracker features an inbuilt motion sensor, which allows extremely low battery usage while the device is stationary. This allows for long term tracking and can be remotely re-configured to alter the tracking rate. They contain a vendor-provided global SIM card which would ensure tracking continued if the bicycle ended up in another country.

The standard batteries in the Tracki unit were replaced to extend the runtime, as we felt the stock 600mAh Li-Ion battery may not provide enough tracking time. Attempts to utilise three Energiser Ultimate Lithium AA batteries were unsuccessful as the tracker’s battery protection circuit shut down the unit detecting an over-voltage condition. Instead, we utilised six AA alkaline batteries in one tracker (wired in 3S2P configuration, approximately 6000mah). A single 18650 Li-Ion battery was used in a second unit to provide approximately 2500mah. Two of the removed stock Tracki batteries were then used in parallel for the third tracker (approximately 1200mah).

The unit with six alkaline batteries continued working for 3 months and 13 days. This contained a combination of two highly active weeks with frequent updates, with the remaining being low movement days.

2.2. Locks

Three \$35 AUD folding bicycle locks were obtained from Amazon. We selected these as they give the appearance of a higher end bicycle, compared to merely utilising a cable lock.

During the experiment one folding lock key set was lost. The lock was destroyed by one of our researchers in order to recover the bicycle and subsequently replaced with a very inexpensive cable lock purchased from a major supermarket. This bicycle was never stolen, even when using the insecure cable lock.

Figure 1: Frame cutout used to place GPS tracker inside

3. Results

Two of the three bicycles were stolen and successfully tracked over multiple months.

-	Days on street	Locations	Days tracked
Trinx	22	4	82
Transit	15	2	89
Step Through	130+	6	-

3.1. Reid Transit Commuter

The Reid Transit Commuter retailed at ~\$400 AUD with second hand sale prices typically ranging from \$70-\$300 on Facebook marketplace and Gumtree.

To prepare it for tracking, a hole was cut in the frame just above the bottom bracket. The GPS tracker and batteries were subsequently placed in the hole. (Figure 1) This was packed with cloth to ensure the equipment would not rattle, and the hole covered with a sheet of shaped perspex to match the original shape of the bicycle’s frame. This was secured in place with epoxy adhesive. A helmet warning sticker was then designed by our researchers, which was applied over the top of the perspex to conceal our modifications, and a layer of transparent car paint / headlight protector plastic film was then adhered over the top in order to make removal difficult.

The bicycle was locked up in a known bicycle theft hot spot in the Melbourne CBD.

After a month of no movement, the bicycle was then relocated a street away where it was finally stolen a few days later.

By chance the bicycle was later spotted by a research member during a lunch break. No attempt was made to interact with the rider. (Figure 4)

Over the period of a week the bicycle made several journeys around the city. These journeys occurred at

Figure 2: Our helmet warning sticker applied.

Figure 3: The first location the bicycle was locked up at.

Figure 4: Bicycle after it had been stolen

Figure 5: Giant logo decal applied

varied hours of the day and didn't follow a typical commuter pattern. During this time Facebook Marketplace and Gumtree were searched daily for the bicycle using several keywords including but not limited to "bike", "reid", "transit" and "bicycle".

After this daily use pattern the bicycle then reported location at a property in Pascoe Vale. It remained until the tracker's battery expired.

Reconnaissance was performed in the area multiple times indicating that it wasn't abandoned in a public place, but we theorised from the lack of movement that it had not been resold.

3.2. *Trinx M136 Mountain Bike 26 inch*

The Trinx bicycle was modified in a similar way to the Reid Transit. The bicycle was originally left locked at Springvale station, later moved to Westall station and Balaclava station when no theft was observed.

After 17 days the bicycle was recovered to replace the batteries and perform some cosmetic modifications. It was identified at this point that the bar end grips had been removed from the handlebars by an unknown party. These were not replaced. The decals were overlaid with a fake "GIANT" logo on the frame and "UL-TEGEGRA" (sic) logo on the cranks. The intention was to increase the perceived value of the bicycle and make it easier to identify in listings.

The bicycle was then locked to a rack in Richmond where it was stolen 6 days later. After initially being taken to a bar, the bicycle remained at a residential location for 4 days before being moved to a house in Reservoir for the following month. It then moved to a property in a commercial / shopping area.

Like the Reid Transit attempts were made to locate the bicycle in public areas around the reported location, but these were again unsuccessful indicating that this bicycle was also likely not abandoned or sold.

3.3. *Reid Ladies Classic Vintage Bike*

A step-through Reid bicycle was installed with the GPS tracker hidden in a 3D printed oversized rear re-

Figure 6: Example of the tracking data provided

Figure 7: 3d printed replacement reflector housing

reflector housing. (Figure 7)

This bicycle was regularly moved around various locations in the Richmond area, including the exact location the Trinx M136 was stolen from. After a period of 4 months and 15 days it had not been stolen. At this point the experiment was discontinued, the tracker removed, and the bicycle donated to an individual in need of one.

4. Discussion

4.1. Time to theft

Given our prior perceptions of bicycle theft we had believed that these bicycles would be stolen in less than a week. Our results show instead that two of the bicycles lasted for over a month before theft occurred, with one not being stolen after over four months.

While the sample size is too small to form concrete conclusions it highlights that the area is ripe for further research. Researchers should consider factoring in this additional time requirement when designing battery systems for tracking bait bikes - we were convinced that the amount of battery we provided would have been sufficient.

4.2. Time to sale

In one case, the Reid Transit Commuter, was used heavily prior to being moved to another location. This might indicate that the theft wasn't entirely motivated by immediate monetary reward.

Although great effort has been ongoing in performing daily checks of online marketplaces for over 4 months after the theft, at no point have either of the stolen bicycles been seen. Researches should account for this possibility in further research. It also indicates that the bicycles might not be perceived as worth selling in their current form - and may be either used for spare parts or scrap metal.

4.3. Organised crime

As the stolen bicycles were present in residential properties and not moved during our observation window, it could indicate that these locations are used for handling stolen goods. This would align with the research performed in the previously mentioned "Tracking stolen bikes in Amsterdam" [1]. A recent item of media coverage in a closer location [2] reported on an incident of police recovering a significant amount of stolen property from a single location is further evidence that more effort should be made by police to investigate bicycle theft, something currently perceived as a low priority.

4.4. Perceived value

We believe further research is needed in identifying if and how the theft rate may be motivated by the perceived value of the bicycle. As the Trinx bicycle was only stolen after the cosmetic modifications and the Reid step through bicycle remained unstolen it could indicate such a link. This is contrary to our belief that the theft of these bicycles might not be entirely motivated by monetary reward given the lack of evidence of their sale.

4.5. Decal identification

The Trinx decal modification was intended to also aid in identification on online marketplaces. However while the excessively large lettering was made to match the existing style of the Trinx brand, and presumed to be unique enough it was later found to be quite similar to Giant's own styling on some of their bicycle models (Figure 8). Care should be taken when attempting to make a bicycle unique in such a manner.

Figure 8: Our logo left, example Facebook listing right.

4.6. Detection and placement of the GPS tracker

We don't believe the GPS trackers were detected during our observation window as the trackers remained functional for the duration of their battery life and the bicycles were never dumped.

This indicates that placing a GPS tracker under a sticker/label or even decal is most likely sufficient concealment. The advantage of these placement locations is that the tracker isn't at risk of easy detection or unintentional removal compared to the usual locations used such as under seats or on accessories.

The majority of tracking devices today have either buttons or general purpose inputs that can trigger the sending of messages. An area that could be improved upon with this tracking setup would be to utilise these buttons to detect access to the tracker. This could be through a reed switch or foil contacts which trigger the GPS tracker to send a message if the concealed compartment is breached.

Additionally, we investigated alternative GPS tracking devices such as the ZX908. This device is 35mm x 20mm x 5.8mm, smaller than the Tracki unit we used. Its small size creates some alternative mounting locations which may be more covert - such as inside a tubeless tyre.

4.7. Locks and ease of theft

Due to missing keys the Reid step through bicycle was switched from a folding lock to a cable lock. When we had to remove the folding lock without being in possession of the keys, it was found that the lock could very easily be destroyed using nothing more than leverage from the bicycle itself. Low end folding locks may account for the ease or frequency of theft as it can be performed without any tools.

Research should be performed into the real world performance of low end bicycle locks in theft prevention. Many industry rating schemes do already exist such as AXA or Sold Secure, but inexpensive bicycle locks are frequently not rated in these schemes.

5. Declarations

Two bicycles were donated to the project by an anonymous bicycle retailer due to cosmetic damage preventing their sale.

References

- [1] Venverloo T, Duarte F, Benson T, Leoni P, Hoogendoorn S, Ratti C., Tracking stolen bikes in Amsterdam., PLoS One. 2023;18(2):e0279906. Published 2023 Feb 15. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0279906
- [2] Lily Nothling, Police use AirTag on stolen e-bike to find 15 stolen bikes, scooters at Canberra apartment <https://www.abc.net.au/news/2025-07-10/act-policing-locate-15-missing-bikes-and-scooters-via-airtag/105516210> (accessed: 01.10.2025)